

THE SEMILATTICE WITH CONSISTENT RETURN

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Let p be a prime number. In [5] is defined the function S_p as $S_p: N^* \rightarrow N^*$, $S_p(a) = k$, where k is the smallest positive integer so that p^a is a divisor for $k!$.

A Smarandache function of first kind is defined for each $n \in N^*$ in [1], as numerical function $S_n: N^* \rightarrow N^*$, so that:

i) if $n = u^i$, where $u = 1$ or $u = p$, then $S_n(a) = k$, k being the smallest positive integer with the property that $k! = M \cdot u^{ia}$.

ii) if $n = p_1^{i_1} \cdot p_2^{i_2} \cdot \dots \cdot p_r^{i_r}$, then
$$S_n(a) = \max_{1 \leq j \leq r} \{S_{p_j}(i_j a)\}.$$

It is proved that:

$$\sum_1 \quad \max\{S_n(a), S_n(b)\} \leq S_n(a+b) \leq S_n(a) + S_n(b)$$

$$\sum_2 \quad S_n(a+b) \leq S_n(a) \cdot S_n(b)$$

In [2] is proved that:

i) the function S_n is monotonously increasing,

ii) the sequence of functions $\{S_{p^i}\}_{i \in N^*}$ is monotonously increasing.

iii) for p, q - prime numbers such that: $p < q \Rightarrow S_p < S_q$ and $p \cdot i < q \Rightarrow S_{p^i} < S_{q^j}$, where $i \in N^*$

iv) if $n < p$, then $S_n < S_p$.

In [3] it is proved:

i) for $p \geq 5$, $S_p > \max\{S_{p-1}, S_{p+1}\}$

ii) for p, q - prime numbers, $i, j \in N^*$

$$p < q \text{ and } i \leq j \Rightarrow S_{p^i} < S_{q^j}$$

iii) the sequence of functions $\{S_n\}_{n \in N^*}$ is generally increasing boundled

iv) if $n = p_1^{i_1} \cdot p_2^{i_2} \cdot \dots \cdot p_r^{i_r}$, there are $k_1, k_2, \dots, k_m \in \{1, 2, \dots, r\}$ so that for each $t \in \overline{1, m}$ there is $q_t \in N^*$ so that

$$S_n(q_t) = S_{p_{k_t}^{i_{k_t}}}(q_t)$$

and for each $l \in N^*$ we have:

$$S_n(l) = \max_{1 \leq t \leq m} \left\{ S_{p_{k_t}^{i_{k_t}}} (l) \right\}.$$

We define the set $\left\{ p_{k_t}^{i_{k_t}} \mid t \in \overline{1, m} \right\}$ as the set of active factors of n and the others factors as the pasive factors.

Let $N_{p_1 \cdot p_2 \cdots p_r} = \left\{ n = p_1^{i_1} \cdot p_2^{i_2} \cdots p_r^{i_r} \mid i_1, i_2, \dots, i_r \in N^* \right\}$, where $p_1 < p_2 < \cdots < p_r$ are prime numbers.

Then

$$N^{p_1 p_2 \cdots p_r} = \left\{ n \in N_{p_1 p_2 \cdots p_r} \mid n \text{ has } p_1^{i_1}, p_2^{i_2}, \dots, p_r^{i_r} \text{ as active factors} \right\}$$

is the S-active cone.

A Smarandache function of second kind is defined for each $k \in N^*$ in [1], as the function $S^k: N^* \rightarrow N^*$ where $S^k(n) = S_n(k)$.

It is proved that:

$$\sum_3 \quad \max \left\{ S^k(a), S^k(b) \right\} \leq S^k(a \cdot b) \leq S^k(a) + S^k(b)$$

$$\sum_4 \quad S^k(a \cdot b) \leq S^k(a) \cdot S^k(b)$$

In [4] it is proved that:

- i) for $k, n \in N^*$ the formula $S^k(n) \leq n \cdot k$ is true
- ii) all prime numbers $p \geq 5$ are maximal points for S^k and

$$S^k(p) = p \left[k - i_p(k) \right], \quad \text{where } 0 \leq i_p(k) \leq \left[\frac{k-1}{p} \right]$$

iii) the function S^k has its relative minimum values for every $n = p!$, where p is a prime number and $p \geq \max\{3, k\}$

iv) the numbers kp for p prime number, $k \in N^*$ and $p > k$, are the fixed points of S^k

v) the function S^k have the following properties:

a) $S^k = 0 \quad (n^{1+\varepsilon})$, for $\varepsilon > 0$

b) $\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{S^k(n)}{n} = k$

c) S^k is, "generally speaking", increasing, thus:

$$\forall n \in N^*, \exists m_0 \in N \text{ so that } \forall m \geq m_0 \Rightarrow S^k(m) \geq S^k(n)$$

1. **DEFINITION.** Let $\mathcal{M} = \{S_m(n) \mid n, m \in N^*\}$, let $A, B \in \mathcal{P}(N^*) \setminus \emptyset$ and $a = \min A$, $b = \min B$, $a^* = \max A$, $b^* = \max B$. The set I is the set of the functions:

$$I_A^B: N^* \rightarrow \mathcal{M}, \text{ with } I_A^B(n) = \begin{cases} S_a(b), n < \max\{a, b\} \\ S_{a_k}(b_k), \max\{a, b\} \leq n \leq \max\{a^*, b^*\} \\ S_{a^*}(b^*), n > \max\{a^*, b^*\} \end{cases}$$

where

$$a_k = \max_i \{a_i \in A \mid a_i \leq n\}$$

$$b_k = \max_j \{b_j \in B \mid b_j \leq n\}$$

2. EXAMPLES.

a) $I_{\{3,8,10\}}^{\{6,10,12\}}: N^* \rightarrow \mathcal{M}$ and:

n	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	$n \geq 13$
$I_{\{3,8,10\}}^{\{6,10,12\}}$	$S_3(6)$	$S_8(6)$	$S_8(6)$	$S_{10}(10)$	$S_{10}(10)$	$S_{10}(12)$	$S_{10}(12)$						

b) Let $A = \{1, 3, 5, \dots, 2k+1, \dots\}$

$$B = \{2, 4, 6, \dots, 2k, \dots\}$$

$I_A^B: N^* \rightarrow \mathcal{M}$ and:

n	1	2	3	4	5	6	...	2k	2k+1	...
I_A^B	$S_2(1)$	$S_2(1)$	$S_2(3)$	$S_4(3)$	$S_4(5)$	$S_6(5)$	...	$S_{2k}(2k-1)$	$S_{2k}(2k+1)$	...

c) Let $A = \{5, 9, 10\}$ and $I_A^A, I_{N^*}^{N^*}: N^* \rightarrow \mathcal{M}$ with

n	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	$n \geq 11$
I_A^A	$S_5(5)$	$S_9(9)$	$S_{10}(10)$	$S_{10}(10)$							
$I_{N^*}^{N^*}$	$S_1(1)$	$S_2(2)$	$S_3(3)$	$S_4(4)$	$S_5(5)$	$S_6(6)$	$S_7(7)$	$S_8(8)$	$S_9(9)$	$S_{10}(10)$	$S_n(n)$

It is easy to see that I_A^A is not the reduction of $I_{N^*}^{N^*}$ and $I_A^A(N^*) \subset I_{N^*}^{N^*}(N^*)$.

3. REMARK.

The functions which belongs to the set I have the following properties :

1) if $A_1 \subset A_2$ and $n \in A_1$, then $I_{A_1}^B(n) = I_{A_2}^B(n)$

1') if $B_1 \subset B_2$ and $n \in B_1$, then $I_A^{B_1}(n) = I_A^{B_2}(n)$

2) $I_{N^*}^{N^*}(n) = S_n(n) = S^n(n)$, the function $I_{N^*}^{N^*}$ is called the I -diagonal function and $I_{N^*}^{N^*}(N^*)$ is called the diagonal of $\mathcal{M}$.

3) for each $m \in N^*$ $I_{\{m\}}^{N^*} = S_m$ for $I_{\{m\}}^{N^*}(n) = S_m(n), \forall n \in N^*$.

3') for each $m \in N^*$ $I_{N^*}^{\{m\}} = S^m$ for $I_{N^*}^{\{m\}}(n) = S_n(m) = S^m(n), \forall n \in N^*$,

4) if $n \in A \cap B$, then $I_A^B(n) = I_{\{n\}}^B(n) = S_n(n)$.

4. DEFINITION. For each pair $m, n \in N^*$, $S_m(n)$ and $S^m(n)$ are called the simmetrical numbers relative to the diagonal of $\mathcal{M}$.

S_m and S^m are called the simmetrical functions relative to the I-diagonal function $I_{N^*}^{N^*}$. As a rule, I_A^B and I_B^A are called the simmetrical functions relative to the I-diagonal function $I_{N^*}^{N^*}$.

5. DEFINITION. Let us consider the following rule $\top: I \times I \rightarrow I$, $I_A^B \top I_C^D = I_{A \cup C}^{B \cup D}$. It is easy to see that $\top$ is idempotent, commutative and associative, so that:

i) $I_A^B \top I_A^B = I_A^B$

ii) $I_A^B \top I_C^D = I_C^D \top I_A^B$

iii) $(I_A^B \top I_C^D) \top I_E^F = I_A^B \top (I_C^D \top I_E^F)$, where $A, B, C, D, E, F \in \mathcal{P}(N^*) \setminus \emptyset$

6. DEFINITION. Let us consider the following relative partial order relation ρ , where:

$$\rho \subset I \times I,$$

$$I_A^B \rho I_C^D \Leftrightarrow A \subset C \text{ and } B \subset D.$$

It is easy to see that $(I, \top, \rho)$ is a semilattice.

7. **DEFINITION.** The elements $u, v \in I$ are ρ - preceded if there is $w \in I$ so that:

$$w \rho u \text{ and } w \rho v.$$

8. **DEFINITION.** The elements $u, v \in I$, are ρ - strictly preceded by w if:

i) $w \rho u$ and $w \rho v$.

ii) $\forall x \in I \setminus \{w\}$ so that $x \rho u$ and $x \rho v \Rightarrow x \rho w$.

9. **DEFINITION.** Let us defined:

$$I^* = \{(u, v) \in I \times I \mid u, v \text{ are } \rho\text{-preceded}\}$$

$$I^\# = \{(u, v) \in I \times I \mid u, v \text{ are } \rho\text{-strictly preceded}\}.$$

It is evidently that $(u, v) \in I^* \Leftrightarrow (v, u) \in I^*$ and $(u, v) \in I^\# \Leftrightarrow (v, u) \in I^\#$.

10. **DEFINITION.** Let us consider $\top^\# = U \times U$, $U \subset I$ and let us consider the following rule:

$\perp: I^\# \rightarrow W$, $W \subset I$, $I_A^B \perp I_C^D = I_{A \wedge C}^{B \wedge D}$ and the ordering partial relation $r \subset U \times U$ so that $I_A^B r I_C^D \Leftrightarrow I_C^D \rho I_A^B$.

The structure $(I^\#, \perp, r)$ is called the return of semilattice $(I, \top, \rho)$.

11. **DEFINITION.** The following set

$$\mathcal{B} = \{I_A^B \in I \mid A \cap B \neq \emptyset\}$$

is called the base of return $(I^\#, \perp, r)$.

12. **REMARK.** The base of return has the following properties:

i) if $I_A^B \in \mathcal{B} \Rightarrow I_B^A \in \mathcal{B}$

ii) for $\emptyset \neq X \subset N^*$, $I_X^X \in \mathcal{B}$

iii) for $I_A^B \in \mathcal{B}$ is true the following equivalence $\emptyset \neq X \subset C_{N^*}(A \wedge B) \Leftrightarrow$ non existence of $I_X^X \perp I_A^B$.

13. **PROPOSITION.** For $I_A^B \in \mathcal{B}$ there exists $n \in N^*$ so that $I_A^B(n) = I_{N^*}^{N^*}(n)$.

Proof. Because $A \cap B \neq \emptyset$ it results that there exists $n \in A \wedge B$ so that:

$$I_A^B(n) = S_n(n) = I_{N^*}^{N^*}(n).$$

It results that for $I_A^B \in \mathcal{B}$ then I_A^B has at least a point of contact with I-diagonal function.

14. **REMARK.** From the 1. it results:

$$I_{\{n\}}^B(n) = S_n(b_n), \text{ where } b_n = \begin{cases} b, n < b = \min B \\ b_k, b \leq n \leq b^* = \max B \\ \text{where} \\ b_k = \max\{x \in B \mid x \leq n\} \\ b^*, n > b^* \end{cases}$$

and

$$I_A^{\{m\}}(m) = S^m(a_m), \text{ where } a_m = \begin{cases} a, m < a = \min A \\ a_k, a \leq m \leq a^* = \max A \\ \text{where} \\ a_k = \max\{x \in A \mid x \leq m\} \\ a^*, m > a^* \end{cases}$$

15. **PROPOSITION.** *There are true the following equivalences:*

$$(I_A^B, I_C^D) \in I^\# \Leftrightarrow I_A^C, I_B^D \in \mathcal{B} \Leftrightarrow \exists n, m \in N^* \text{ so that:}$$

$$I_A^B(n) = I_{\{n\}}^B(n) = S_n(b_n), I_C^D(n) = I_{\{n\}}^D(n) = S_n(d_n), I_A^B(m) = I_A^{\{m\}}(m) = S^m(a_m), \text{ and} \\ I_C^D(m) = I_C^{\{m\}}(m) = S^m(c_m) \text{ where } a_m, b_n, c_m, d_n \text{ are defined in the sense of 14.}$$

If $n \leq m$, then $n \leq a_m, c_m \leq m$.

Proof. Evidently,

$$(I_A^B, I_C^D) \in I^\# \Leftrightarrow A \cap C \neq \emptyset \text{ and } B \cap D \neq \emptyset \Leftrightarrow I_A^C, I_B^D \in \mathcal{B}.$$

Because $A \cap C \neq \emptyset$ and $B \cap D \neq \emptyset$ it exists $n \in A \cap C$ and $m \in B \cap D$. Then:

$$I_A^B(n) = I_{\{n\}}^B(n) = S_n(b_n), I_C^D(n) = I_{\{n\}}^D(n) = S_n(d_n) \\ I_A^B(m) = I_A^{\{m\}}(m) = S^m(a_m), I_C^D(m) = I_C^{\{m\}}(m) = S^m(c_m).$$

Conversely, if there exist $n \in N^*$ so that $I_A^B(n) = S_n(b_n)$ and $I_C^D(n) = S_n(d_n)$, then because $I_A^B(n) = S_n(b_n)$ it results $n = a_k = \max_i \{a_i \in A \mid a_i \leq n\}$, so that $n \in A$. Because $I_C^D(n) = S_n(d_n)$ it results $n \in C$.

Therefore $A \cap C \neq \emptyset$, thus, finally, $I_A^C \in \mathcal{B}$. It is also proved $I_B^D \in \mathcal{B}$ in the some way.

If $n \leq m$, because $n \in A \cap C$ it results that $n \in \{x \in A \mid x \leq m\}$ and $n \in \{y \in C \mid y \leq m\}$, therefore $n \leq a_m \leq m$ and $n \leq c_m \leq m$.

This is presented in the following scheme:

16. DEFINITION. The return $(L^\#, \perp, r)$ of semilattice $(L, \top, \rho)$ is:

- | | |
|-------------------|---|
| a) null, if | $L^\# = \{(u, u) u \in L\} = \Delta_L$. |
| b) weak, if | $\text{card} L^\# < \text{card}(L \times L \setminus L^\#)$ |
| c) consistent, if | $\text{card} L^\# = \text{card}(L \times L - L^\#)$ |
| d) vigour, if | $\text{card} L^\# > \text{card}(L \times L - L^\#)$ |
| e) total, if | $L^\# = L \times L$. |

17. PROPOSITION. The return $(I^\#, \perp, r)$ of the semilattice $(I, \top, \rho)$ is consistent.

Proof. Evidently, $\text{card}(\mathcal{P}(N^*) \setminus \emptyset) = \aleph$, $\text{card} I = \text{card}[(\mathcal{P}(N^*) - \emptyset) \times (\mathcal{P}(N^*) - \emptyset)] = \aleph$ and $\text{card}(I \times I) = \aleph$.

Let us consider $\mathcal{F} = \{(A, C) | A, C \in \mathcal{P}(N^*) - \emptyset, A \cap C = \emptyset\}$ and $\overline{\mathcal{F}} = \{(A, C) | A, C \in \mathcal{P}(N^*) - \emptyset, A \cap C \neq \emptyset\}$.

$\text{card} \mathcal{F} = \text{card} \overline{\mathcal{F}} = \aleph$. Indeed, if $A \cap C = \emptyset$ it results that $C_{N^*} \cdot A \cup C_{N^*} \cdot C = N^*$; because for every $X \in \mathcal{P}(N^*) - \emptyset \exists Y = N^* \setminus X$ so that $X \cup Y = N^*$ then it results $\text{card} \overline{\mathcal{F}} = \text{card} \mathcal{P}(N^*) = \aleph$. Because for each (A, C) , $A, C \in \mathcal{P}(N^*) - \emptyset, A \cap C = \emptyset$, it exist at least two $(A_1, C_1), (A_2, C_2)$ with $A_1 \cap C_1 \neq \emptyset, A_2 \cap C_2 \neq \emptyset$ it results $\text{card} \overline{\mathcal{F}} \geq \text{card} \mathcal{F} = \aleph$.

Since $\text{card}\overline{\mathcal{F}} \leq \text{card}[(\mathcal{P}(N^*) - \emptyset) \times (\mathcal{P}(N^*) - \emptyset)] = \aleph$ finally $\text{card}\overline{\mathcal{F}} = \aleph$. Because $\text{card}I^\# = \text{card}(\overline{\mathcal{F}} \times \overline{\mathcal{F}}) = \aleph$ and $\text{card}(I \times I) - I^\# = \text{card}(\overline{\mathcal{F}} \times \overline{\mathcal{F}}) = \aleph$ it results that $(I^\#, \perp, r)$ is a return consistent.

18. **REMARK.** Generally, it is interesting the following problems:

i) what relations, operations, structures can be defined on

$$M = \{S_m(n) \mid n, m \in N^*\}?$$

ii) what relations, operations, structures can be defined on

$$\mathcal{H} = \{f \mid f: N^* \rightarrow \mathcal{M}\}?$$

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